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[https://doi.org/ 10.5281/zenodo.5851213](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5851213)

USE OF TECHNOLOGY IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING AND TEACHING

Annotation: *As English language plays a key role in several spheres such as education, industries, politics, media, library, business, communication around the world, the article considers the use of technology in English language learning and teaching.*

Key words: *teaching methods, education, and language learning process.*

Due to the massive number of English learners are increasing tremendously different teaching methods have been implemented to test the effectiveness in the teaching process. At present, the onset of technology has drastically changed the old manners of teaching English. With the influence of the phenomenon called globalization which is interrelated with technology, education, work. And culture has been affected positively.

Nowadays, English language plays a key role in several spheres such as education, industries, politics, media, library, business, communication around the world. Technology provides a plethora of options in order to make English teaching standards more mesmerizing, besides this characteristic as well this modern technological tool helps students to get involved and learn according to their interest. It has been tested effectively and is accepted in teaching English in the contemporary society. With the spread and development of English around the world, English has been learnt and is being used by more and more speakers. English Language teaching has been with us for many years and is keeping on growing, fueled, partially by Internet. In 2000, there were a billion English learners but twenty years later, the statistics tripled. On the other hand, over 85 % of the data stored in internet is in English. At present, there are more Non-native than native who uses the English language.

The rapid development of science and technology in this contest we can see the application of Multimedia technology in technology in teaching, featuring audio, visual, animation effects comes into full play in English class teaching and sets a favorable platform for reform and exploration on English teaching model at the present.

To face the new reality which is related about the increasing of English, new teachers are needed to be instructed to guide students in a successful teaching. ELT gives students a plethora of opportunities to gain confidence and credibility, one of its

characteristics is, that is a new manner of learning and teaching English is more dynamic rather than the old ones.

It is sentimental for language teachers to be aware of the latest and best equipment and to have full knowledge of what is available in many given situations.

Preceptors can use Multimedia Technology to give more colorful, stimulating lecturers. There are many techniques which are applicable in various degrees to language learning process. Some are useful for testing and distance education and some for teaching business English, spoken English, reading, listening or interpreting.

Never let the machine take over the role of the teacher plays or limit function where more traditional ways are superior.

Analysis on Necessity of Application of Multimedia technology to English Teaching:

- To cultivate students' interest in study

Nowadays, multimedia technology is more acceptable because it offers a various resources as visual animation effects naturally and humanly makes us more access to information besides, Multimedia technology offers a sense of reality and function very well, which greatly cultivates students' interest.

- To promote students' communication capacity

Traditional manner of teaching language has hampered the process of learning and makes students very passive in understanding the structure, meaning the function of the language, this makes hard to achieve the target of communication. Multimedia technology seeks the integration all aspects in the teaching and learning language. This dynamic way in teaching and learning language motivates students and makes the activities more enjoyable and relaxing. So, Multimedia technology teaching has uniquely inspired students' positive thinking and communication skills in social practice.

- To improve teaching effectiveness

Multimedia teaching enriches teaching content and improves class efficiency. The utilization of multimedia sound lab materializes the individualized and co-operative teaching. Multimedia technology goes beyond time and space, creates more vivid, visual, authentic environment for English learning stimulates students' initiatives and economizes class time, meanwhile, increases class information.

- To improve interaction between teacher and student

Multimedia teaching stresses the key role of student and enhances the importance of interaction between teacher and students. A major feature of multimedia is to train and improve students' ability to listen and speak, and to develop their communicative competence. During this process, the teachers' role as a facilitator is particularly prominent.

- Provide flexibility to course content

Multimedia teaching is flexible. English teaching itself must focus on the guidance of teachers and be student-centered, which we believe is one of the principals for the language teaching.

Multimedia is a contemporary and pragmatic tool which makes the teaching and learning time in classroom more dynamic, energetic, however, it ought not to replace the seminal role of teacher who plays as a guide. The human factor allows students to interact from the pre and during the process of learning language. We have to be aware that we cannot throw away some extra resources like the blackboard where may explanations can be given to let students gain a solid knowledge of the language they are learning. A good teaching happens when students have the opportunity to think on their own way in the process of learning and this is possible by the actions of the teacher who should use the cutting edge technology but in the right way.

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